

GENESIS OF MUHAMMAS IN ORAL FOLK ART

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Abstract. In literature, each genre has its own genesis, biography, theory, gradual development, artistic development, specific characteristics, laws, form and content. This article discusses the importance of folklore in the development of genres, and the role of Uzbek folk songs in the genesis of the muhammas genre is scientifically and theoretically researched.

Key words. Oral folk art (folklore), national tradition, folk songs, epic, dirge, mukhammas, five, style, poetic form, dialect.

I. Introduction

The importance of folk songs in the development of Mukhammas forms is incomparable. If you look at the collection of Uzbek folk songs "*Shoda-shoda marvarid*" collected and prepared for publication by literary scholar Ergash Ochilov, you can find fives in these creations. It is known that folk songs are distinguished by their smooth and simple content, sonority and musicality, richness of various jokes and ironies, unique allusions and expressions.

II. Main part

Scientist E. Ochilov emphasized the important place of folk songs in the nation's thinking and way of life, saying that "these songs express the will and immortal spirit of the people, which has not been broken by any prohibitions of any era" [4, 3]. Although it does not fully meet the requirements of the nature of the genre, the weight of the dream, and the idealistic and artistic perfection, the fives created in folk art can be recognized as the first examples of this genre. For example:

*Ta'rif etay bir yor aslin:
Man shu kun Ra'noni go'rdim.
Orzu etib oning vaslin,
Man shu kun Ra'noni go'rdim,
Qoshlari qaroni go'rdim.*

Naqarot:

*G'ordim, go'rdim – nani go'rdim?
Qoshlari qaroni go'rdim.
Ra'no degan bog'da kezar,
Yoqasina dugma duzar,
Oshiqlarning bag'rin ezar,
Man shu kun Ra'noni go'rdim,
Qoshlari qaroni go'rdim [4, 29].*

[Let me give you a description:

I saw Rana that day.

A dream is his appearance,

I saw Rana today.

I saw his dark eyebrows.

Refrain:

I saw, I saw - what did I see?

I saw his dark eyebrows.

He walks in the garden called Rana,

Buttons on the collar

The heart of lovers

I saw Rana today.

I saw his dark eyebrows]

This song, which is considered one of the best songs of Khorezm people, consists of 6 stanzas. Although this song is written in finger weight, and the rhyming system is not exactly similar to mukhammas, the fact that the stanzas consist of 5 verses, the repetition of two lines at the end of the stanza, and the development of the thoughts of the first stanza in the following stanzas can be noted as elements typical of mukhammas.

In most of the folk songs, there is a repetition of verses that provide melodiousness and fluency, and this is also related to the aspect related to mukhammas. "Tarje" in Arabic means to return, to repeat.

In mukhammas, tarje' appears in two different forms: 1) verse tarje' (two verses are repeated in a stanza); 2) translation of the verse (one verse is repeated in the stanza). Two different types of tarje can be found in folk songs. For example, in the song dedicated to "Sunbula", the sixth of the twelve zodiac signs according to the lunar calendar, which is located between Asad and Mezon, the verse is repeated in all verses of the verse "Qadamingga gullar ochilsin" progress can be followed:

*Sunbula-yu, sunbula,
O'rab olay gul bilan.
Mening ko'nghim sen bilan-o,
Sen ketasan kim bilan?
Qadamingga gullar ochilsin!
Men bu yerda o't yoqsam,
Farg'onada tutuni.
Bu dunyoda bormikan
Yurak bag'ri butuni?
Qadamingga gullar ochilsin! [4, 15]*

This song, consisting of five verses, created because of events, testifies to the high artistic thinking of the people. The lover logically finds an answer to the

rhetorical question of whether there is a person with a whole heart in this world. Of course, in this world, it is desirable to meet a person whose heart is full, who is free from sadness, who is always happy. If there is such a person, he will make a stove out of paper and make firewood out of flowers. Paper-furnace, flower-wood, which are presented as an excellent example of contrast, strengthen the image in the verses and point to the complete absence of a person. Even so, the unrequited lover wants only good things for him. Even when he left with someone else, he said to him with pain and anguish, "*Qadamingga gullar ochilsin!*" he admits to his fate. Although this song, infused with deep pain in its essence, is not exactly similar to mukhammas in terms of weight, its formal elements and content indicate that the mukhammas genre grew out of folk oral creativity. Literary scholar D. Hakimov, who studied the formation of mukhammas genre in the Persian-Tajik literature of the 12th-19th centuries, notes that the examples of folk oral works were created in different periods of Aruz, and although in some places there are defects in the rhyme, they fully meet the rules of mukhammas [3, 14-15]. The fact that we call the quintessences used in this passage as excellent examples is based on the rhyming order of the passage (although there is a flaw in the first stanza), the integrity of the content, and the fact that it consists of five stanzas.

III. Conclusion

In conclusion, it should be noted that the genesis of the mukhammas genre goes back to folk songs and epics. The reason why it is related to epics is that epics also contain wonderful examples of folk songs, and fives are a product of folk artistic thinking. During the emergence, formation, and development of written literature, poets and creators, along with creating epics, connecting tahmis, and continuing the traditional spirit in literature, enriched it with new tones, means of expression, and images typical of the era, and created new classical poetry; those who managed to breathe in. In their work, the attitude to words and music, the folk musical tone was particularly distinguished.

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